

TECHNOLOGY OF TEACHING STUDENTS TO CRITICAL THINKING BASED ON INDIVIDUAL APPROACH

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Abstract. *Lessons using technology for teaching critical thinking are different from lessons in traditional teaching.*

The article highlights the content of pedagogical technologies for students to share their thoughts with each other, read, write and discuss what they have read based on an individual approach.

Keywords: *critical thinking, lesson, reading, writing, insert, technology, method, skill, ability.*

In order to increase the effectiveness of training and development of talented students, to fundamentally improve the quality of higher education, to study foreign languages, computer science and other important and high-demand subjects such as mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology in an in-depth manner, to engage children in mass sports, music and art. construction of sports schools, reconstruction of existing ones is one of the priority directions.

The conceptual basis of preparing future teachers for education and development of gifted students is described in the researches of Sh. Mardonov [2], O. Musurmonova [3], S. Nishonova [5] and others.

The technology of teaching students to think critically on the basis of an individual approach determines the indicators of the student's ability to self-motivate, emotional-volitional self-development, emotional self-control, the development of research activities of the intellectual component, and the development of analytical thinking of the creative component [1].

Lessons using technology for teaching critical thinking are different from lessons in traditional teaching. Pupils do not sit passively listening to the teacher, but become the main characters of the lesson, they think and remember, share their thoughts with each other, read, write, discuss what they have read.

This technology reflects only a small part of the existing methodological developments and is aimed at general introduction of teachers to the technology of developing critical thinking, which allows the teacher to use a universal educational model and a system of effective methods, helps students to be independent, think critically, responsibly and creatively. This creates a real opportunity to create a collaborative environment in the classroom (group). The teacher teaches to work in a creative cooperation mode based on technology, to be ready for rational changes, to make non-standard and responsible decisions.

The word "technology" comes from the Greek words "techne" - art, skill, ability and "logos" - science, law. Literally, "technology" is the science of skill. Technology is a set of techniques used in any business, skill, art (explanatory dictionary). Pedagogical technologies are a set of means and methods of organizing the educational process (education, training and personal

development processes), which ensure the achievement of educational goals according to pre-defined criteria [4].

Pedagogical technology is a set of methods of organizing the learning process or a sequence of certain actions and operations (technological chain) related to the specific activities of the teacher and aimed at achieving goals.

Pedagogical technologies create an opportunity to manage the processes of education, upbringing and development of students and provide solutions to modern educational problems. If methods and methods "how to educate students?" How to teach them?' answers the questions, technologies analyze how to do this optimally.

From the point of view of implementation of educational issues, the following technologies are relevant:

- Information and communication technologies
- Technologies for developing critical thinking
- Design technologies
- Developmental educational technologies
- Healthcare technologies
- Problematic educational technologies
- Game technologies
- Modular technology
- workshop technology
- case technologies
- Integrated educational technologies
- Pedagogy of cooperation.
- stratification technology
- Group technologies.

The result of using pedagogical technologies:

- quality of education;
- high motivation for learning;
- development of creative potential;
- ability to work independently;
- leads to the development of cognitive activity.

Critical thinking is formed primarily through discussions, writings, and active engagement with texts. In order for students to become familiar with these forms of work, they need only be slightly modified. For example, on the basis of an individual approach, in teaching students to think critically, it is possible to find existing general information, form graphic structures, exchange ideas and achieve unity through the "Insert" method.

This technology allows each student to react to the text by placing marks on the basis of the knowledge obtained by quickly reading the topic. Each important concepts and ideas in the text of the lecture are marked with appropriate symbols, and the following table is compiled from them:

The content of the main concepts and basic phrases of the topic	I know	New information for me	He denied the information I knew	Got me thinking (I don't get it)
	V	+	-	?
1.	V			
2.				?
3.		+		
4.			-	

INSERT is an English acronym that literally translates to Interactive Note-taking System for Effective Reading and Thinking (authors - Vaughan and Estes, 1986, modified by Meredith and Steele, 1997). Admission is done in several stages.

Step 1: A text labeling system is proposed to divide the data into:

- to determine the ownership of certain concepts on a new topic, forms the skill of analytical approach to the text;
- develops students' critical thinking, introduces new information;
- forms the skills of independent work with literature;
- arouses interest in reading, expands the worldview, forms the ability to work independently with scientific literature.

y - symbol is assigned to things known to students;

- things that contradict the students' opinion are marked with a minus sign;

+ sign indicates what is interesting for them and unexpected information;

? If something is unclear, there is a desire to learn more, a "question mark" is put.

The technology of teaching students to think critically based on an individual approach is based on ideas and rules about the stages of mental development of a child. Children are inquisitive by nature, they want to explore the world, they are able to consider serious issues and come up with original ideas. A teacher's job is to be a facilitator who encourages students to learn relentlessly and helps them develop effective thinking skills.

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